

tive stage to maturity. This means that grain yield for continuous shallow submergence can be achieved with 7-cm irrigation water applied 3 d after disappearance of ponded water, for a net savings of 24% of the water requirement (Table 2).

Applied N higher than 80 kg/ha did not significantly affect yield, and 40 kg N/ha appeared sufficient. The interaction of irrigation and N was not significant. □

Table 2. Effect of irrigation schedule and N level on water requirement and water-use efficiency of summer rice in Assam, India.

Treatment	Rainfall (mm)			Water requirement (mm)			Water-use efficiency (kg/ha/mm)			
	1987	1988	1989	1987	1988	1989	1987	1988	1989	Mean
Continuous submergence	504	1040	519	1304	1640	1149	1.71	0.83	2.30	1.61
7 cm water 1 DADPW	504	1040	519	1204	1390	1009	1.66	1.14	2.71	1.84
7 cm water 3 DADPW	504	1040	519	924	1320	869	2.23	1.23	3.26	2.24

Improving applied phosphorus utilization by rice in Madagascar

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On the Fe-toxic, low-P soils of the Central Highlands of Madagascar, broadcast P fertilizers are fixed by the Fe and poorly utilized by the rice plant. Resource-poor farmers often cannot afford to apply the recommended 26 kg P/ha.

We compared applying 13 kg P/ha (1/2 the recommended rate) by broadcast and incorporation and by seedling root dipping, in a farmer's field in Manjakandriana (1,420 m) for 4 yr. Soil was 49% clay, 21% silt, 30% sand, pH 4.9, and had 3.31% organic C, CEC 10.2 meq, 5.3 ppm available P.

Effect of P rate and method of application on yield of Chianan 8, transplanted on an Fe-toxic soil, Sambaina, Manjakandriana, Madagascar.

Treatment ^a	Yield ^b (t/ha)				
	1985/86	1986/87	1987/88	1988/89	Mean
No fertilizer	2.5 d	0.8 c	0.9 c	1.1 d	1.4
NK only	3.7 c	0.8 c	1.1 c	1.6 c	1.8
NK + 13 kg/ha B/I	3.9 bc	1.3 b	2.3 b	2.2 b	2.4
NK + 13 kg P/ha root dipping	4.2 ab	2.0 a	3.0 a	2.6 a	3.0
NK + 26 kg P/ha B/I	4.4 a	1.4 b	2.4 b	2.2 b	2.6

^a B/I = broadcast and incorporated. N = 60 and K = 50 kg/ha. ^b In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Triple superphosphate (TSP) was dissolved in water and soil was added until a sticky paste was formed (approximately 1:4:6 of TSP, water, and soil). Seedling roots were coated in the paste and immediately transplanted. (The first year, rice roots were dipped in a mixture of water and TSP.) N and K were applied at 60 and 50 kg/ha, respectively.

Averaged over 4 yr, root dipping was 22% more effective than broadcasting

and incorporating TSP, and root dipping with 13 kg P/ha was as effective as broadcasting and incorporating 26 kg P/ha (see table). Leaf tissue analysis showed higher P levels in plants fertilized by seedling root dipping.

Concentrating the P around the roots probably reduces the amount of P fixed by the soil and makes more P immediately available to the rice plant. □

Integrated pest management—diseases

Association of *Fusarium moniliforme* Sheld. with rice seeds and subsequent infection in Pakistan

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Rice bakanae disease caused by *Fusarium moniliforme* Sheld.—perfect stage *Gibberella fujikuroi* Sawada—is becoming a serious threat to rice production in Pakistan. We collected rice seed

samples from nine localities to assess its incidence.

Seeds treated with 0.1% mercuric chloride for 1 min and untreated seeds, 400/sample, were studied. Twenty seeds per sterilized petri plate were plated on three layers of moistened blotter paper and kept at 25 °C in 12 h light, 12 h dark for 7 d. These seeds were examined under a stereoscope; microscopic slides also were studied for identification.

Other seeds from the same samples were grown separately in sterilized pots, and isolations from the vascular system

of the seedlings were made on Richard's agar medium at 27 °C. A third set of seeds was planted and typical bakanae disease symptoms on the mature plants measured.

Seeds from all localities but D. G. Khan showed the presence of *F. moniliforme*. Maximum presence of fungus on seeds was 19.75%. Nearly 20% of the seeds treated with 0.1% mercuric chloride from Gujranwala showed presence of the fungus (see table).

When the seeds were not treated before plating, highest fungus infection was near 12% in those from Sialkot. In most cases, fungus intensity was higher

in treated seeds, showing that the fungus was internally borne, or at least present inside the seed coat.

Seedlings produced from the seed samples confirmed the presence of fungus in the vascular system. Bakanae symptoms appeared on plants grown to maturity.

Reisolation of the pathogen and back-inoculation to other rice plants confirmed its pathogenicity. □

Effect of grain discoloration in upland rice on some yield components

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The main causal agents of grain discoloration (GD) in upland rice in West Sumatra are different species of fungi, with *Helminthosporium oryzae* being the most important. Symptoms vary from spots invisible to the naked eye to a completely rotten endosperm. In susceptible varieties, the disease can cause complete yield loss.

We collected 50 panicles of susceptible upland rice variety Tondano in the Sitiung area and separated them into five groups, with disease severities of 1, 10, 30, 60, and 100%. Seeds of each severity

Rice seeds from different localities showing percent bakanae disease infection in Pakistan.

Locality	Seeds ^a showing <i>F. moniliforme</i> (%)		Seedlings showing <i>F. moniliforme</i> in vascular system (%)	Bakanae disease symptoms (%) in plants grown from untreated seeds
	Treated ^b	Untreated		
Amin Abad	9.5	6.2	10	6
Daska	6.0	1.5	6	7
G. G. Khan	0.0	0.0	0	0
Gujranwala	19.8	9.5	17	8
Hafiz Abad	11.0	7.2	12	7
Kala Shah Kaku	12.2	5.5	10	9
Narang Mandi	8.8	1.8	9	11
Sheikhupura	11.5	7.2	13	11
Sialkot	12.2	11.8	10	9

^aMean of 4 counts. ^bWith 0.1% mercuric chloride for 1 min.

group were planted in plastic trays (33 seeds/tray per replication) and grown in the greenhouse, to determine the effect of the disease on germination and plant height. Additional panicles of each severity group (3 panicles/replication) were used to study the effect of disease on grains/panicle. Weight of 100 grains was calculated for each severity group,

with three replications.

The higher the disease severity, the lower the germination and seedling height (see table). The disease reduced germination as much as 40% and reduced seedling height 3-20%. The higher the severity, the more the empty grains/panicle, with parallel weight reduction. □

Effect of rice grain discoloration on some yield components.^a

Severity of grain discoloration (%)	Germination ^b (%)	Seedling height ^c (cm)	Grains (no./panicle)				Weight of 100 grains ^e (g)	Reduction in weight (%10)
			Filled ^d	%	Empty	%		
1	92 a	10.9 (91) a	140 a	94	9 b	6	3.09 a	-
10	81 a	10.6 (86) a	137 a	90	16 b	10	2.94 a	5
30	80 bc	10.2 (79) a	135 a	91	14 b	9	2.95 a	4
60	73 c	9.7 (72) ab	101 b	74	35 a	26	2.56 b	17
100	52 d	8.7 (52) b	118 b	78	33 a	22	2.27 c	26

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not statistically different at a probability level of 0.05. ^bAv from 3 replications, 33 seeds/replication. ^cAv from 3 replications. Values in parentheses are total number of seedlings. ^dAv from 3 replications, 3 panicles/replication. ^eAv from 3 replications, 100 seeds/replication.

Integrated pest management—insects

Duration of diapause in white stem borer (SB) *Scirpophaga innotata*

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The white SB replaced the yellow SB *S. incertulas* in many parts of the northern coast of West Java in the 1989-90 wet season.

Replacement of improved Cisadane, a

135-d variety, with IR64 (110 d) lengthened the fallow period between dry and wet season crops to 3 mo. That favored the white SB, which can aestivate as prepupae at the base of rice stubble. The outbreak destroyed 15,000 ha of rice in the command area of the Jatiluhur Irrigation System (JIS) in Karawang, Subang, and Indramayu districts.

The JIS is divided into five regions of staggered water delivery. At Sukamandi, rice is transplanted ahead of that in Karawang. We collected aestivating prepupae from Karawang (52 d after

harvest) and Sukamandi (96 d after harvest) and subjected them to artificial rainfall and to flooding, to simulate land preparation for rice.

Frequency and amount of rainfall was based on the previous year's pattern. Water was poured onto prepupae in rice stubble placed in pots. Excised prepupae were placed individually in 12-cm-long, 0.5-cm-dim plastic drinking straws with cotton plugs in both ends. The straws were placed with the bottom cotton plug in contact with standing water, to simulate flooding.

Both watering methods terminated aestivation. The prepupae in the untreated